

Promoting organizational citizenship behavior through ethical leadership: The education context

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the impact of ethical leadership on employees' organizational citizenship behavior. To enhance the conceptual understanding of the study, an extensive literature review was conducted. Employing an assessment and correlational research design, the study targeted the entire employee population of the Divine Word College of Laoag. Research questionnaires were utilized for data collection, with data analyzed using weighted mean and Pearson correlation coefficient (r). Results revealed a significant correlation between administrators' ethical leadership and organizational citizenship behavior concerning OCBP. However, no correlation was found between ethical leadership and organizational citizenship behavior associated with OCBO.

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Introduction

The topic of leadership has been the centre of interest of social scientists because of its great importance for society. The topic has been discussed from different perspectives and focuses. For example, Avolio and Bass (1986, 1994) discussed transformational leadership with its four components namely idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration. These are the four ways that can be used by a leader to transform an organization. Bass (1990) discussed transactional leadership which focuses on

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reward management in which the employees are rewarded after they achieve the targeted objectives. Though both leadership styles contain moral principles like leading by example and in the case of transactional leadership espouses honesty, fairness, responsibility and honoring commitments (Burns, 1978), however, they have not specifically discussed directly on ethical leadership directly and its effect on performance. Many other researchers have been doing research measuring the effect of the two leadership styles on performance (Bass, 1985), but there has been little attention given to ethical leadership as admitted by Brown and Trevino (2006).

Nowadays, the interest in ethical leadership has gained momentum because of what is happening in society like corruption and corporate bankruptcies. These two phenomena are always linked to the moral values of all who manage and work in the government and private corporations (Hassan, 2015, Tang, et.al., 2015). Two well-known examples of corporate bankruptcies related to unethical misconduct and corporate governance failures are the case of Enron and WorldCom (Bukhari, 2019, Romar & Calkins, 2006). Besides government agencies and financial institutions, cases of unethical misconduct can also happen in other industries like education. Unethical misconduct in education can be related to justice and equality, respect for others, professional integrity and compliance with organizational culture (Yildirim, et.al., 2019). Or it may involve other cases like bias in grading, research plagiarism and abuse of authority (Ishak, et.al., 2018).

Ethical and unethical leadership brings with them positive and negative outcomes which may be good and bad for the person and the organization. Ethical leadership may attract employees to stay and to be committed (Elci, et.al., 2012), while unethical leadership may negatively influence work attitude and job satisfaction (Ruiz-Palomino, et.al., 2021). Knowing the positive and negative consequences of ethical and unethical leadership motivates the current researcher to investigate the extent of ethical leadership of administrators and how it affects the organizational citizenship behavior of the employees.

The study is divided into several parts. The first part is the introduction which explains the rationale or the background of the study. The second part is the literature review to establish the concept and theories of the study. The third part is the research methodology which contains the research design, population, locale, instruments, research procedures, ethical review and statistical treatment of data. The fourth part is the data presentation and Analysis which presents data on the tables followed by the analysis. The fifth part is the result discussion and conclusion.

Leadership, a pivotal focus for social scientists, has been extensively explored through various lenses. Avolio and Bass (1986, 1994) delineated transformational leadership, emphasizing its four components: idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration, as means for organizational transformation. In contrast, Bass (1990) elucidated transactional leadership, emphasizing reward management tied to achieving objectives, incorporating moral principles such as leading by example and honesty (Burns, 1978). Notably, ethical leadership and its direct impact on performance have received scant attention despite the ethical underpinnings in both styles (Brown & Trevino, 2006). While research has extensively examined the performance implications of transformational and transactional leadership (Bass, 1985), the focus on ethical leadership remains limited.

Contemporary interest in ethical leadership has surged amidst societal challenges like corruption and corporate malfeasance (Hassan, 2015; Tang et al., 2015). Examples such as the Enron and WorldCom scandals underscore the repercussions of ethical lapses and corporate governance failures (Bukhari, 2019; Romar & Calkins, 2006). Notably, unethical behavior transcends industries, manifesting in sectors like education, where misconduct may compromise justice, equality, and professional integrity (Yildirim et al., 2019; Ishak et al., 2018).

Ethical and unethical leadership yield divergent outcomes, influencing employee commitment and job satisfaction (Elci et al., 2012; Ruiz-Palomino et al., 2021). Understanding these consequences motivates the investigation into administrators' ethical leadership and its impact on employee organizational citizenship behavior.

The study comprises several components: an introduction delineating the study's rationale, a literature review to establish theoretical foundations, a methodology section detailing research design and procedures, data presentation and analysis, and a discussion of results and conclusions.

Literature Review

The literature review presents the concept and theories of ethical leadership based on available literature that is relevant to the current research.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

Overview of Leadership and Management

Confusion often arises between the terms "leadership" and "management," leading to their interchangeable use. Individuals occupying managerial positions may struggle to discern whether they should exhibit leadership or management behavior, impacting both work outcomes and team dynamics negatively (Abun, 2018). Understanding the distinction between leadership and management is crucial for individuals in dual roles, such as CEO, who must navigate between leading and managing effectively (Abun, 2018).

Various authors offer differing definitions of leadership. Bennis and Nanus (1985) view leadership as the capacity to articulate and actualize a vision, while Handy (1993) defines it as the ability to formulate and communicate a vision that guides others' efforts (as cited in Silva & Gomes, 2015). Conger (1992) expands on this, describing leadership as the establishment of direction, gaining commitment to that direction, and motivating individuals to achieve it. These definitions underscore the importance of vision in leadership, with vision serving as the guiding force toward the desired organizational future (Abun, 2018). Moreover, effective leadership entails not only articulating a vision but also implementing it through empowerment, which involves granting employees the authority, resources, and autonomy to execute tasks (Bennis & Nanus, 1985; Honold, 1997; Herrenkohl et al., 1999).

Management, too, is defined diversely across literature. Stoner (1995) describes it as a process encompassing planning, organizing, leading, and controlling organizational efforts toward stated goals. Koontz and Weihrich (1988) emphasize management as the art of accomplishing tasks through people in organized groups, highlighting the focus on execution. Fayol (1984) further elaborates on management as a process involving planning, organizing, mobilizing resources, and controlling activities to achieve organizational objectives. Similarly, Haimann and Scott (1970) view management as a social and technical process that utilizes resources, influences human action, and facilitates change to meet organizational goals.

The disparity between leadership and management lies in their fundamental focus. Bennis and Nanus (1985) encapsulate this distinction by stating that managers ensure tasks are performed efficiently, whereas leaders inspire change and influence others toward a shared vision. While both roles involve working with people and achieving objectives, management concentrates on planning, organizing, and controlling to meet goals, while leadership emphasizes vision creation, empowerment, and motivation for change (Wajdi, 2017; Liphadzi et al., 2017). Boynton (2016) identifies key leadership characteristics, including vision clarity, fostering leadership in others, embracing change, leading by example, idea generation, experimentation, and active listening. Recognizing that leadership encompasses elements of management, Baker (2014) proposes a continuum of leadership and management skills, comprising vision, strategy, operations, and tactics. Leadership begins with articulating a compelling vision and extends to translating strategies into operational plans (Boynton, 2016).

A Brief Review of Ethical Leadership and Its Properties

To achieve high organizational performance, ethical leadership, in addition to task-oriented, relational, and change-oriented behaviors, is deemed essential (Yukl et al., 2013). However, the concept of ethical leadership remains ambiguous, with diverse definitions and measurement dimensions across literature. Kanungo (2001) posits that ethical leaders prioritize behaviors benefiting others, driven by accepted beliefs and judgment rather than self-interest, fostering benefits for followers, organizations, and society (Kalshoven et al., 2011). Similarly, Brown, Trevino, and Harrison (2005) underscore integrity, ethical standards, and fair treatment as vital elements of ethical leadership.

Ethical leadership concerns its impact on others' behaviors, emphasizing appropriate conduct, effective communication, and promotion of ethical behavior through reinforcement and decision-making (Brown et al., 2005; Trevino et al., 2003). Research suggests that ethical leadership positively influences employee behavior and organizational performance (Trevino et al., 2003).

The multitude of dimensions (Kalshoven et al.(2011), Wulumbawa, (2008), Barbuto & Wheeler, (2006), Craig and Gustafson (1998) proposed for ethical leadership measurement presents a challenge. De Hoogh and Den Hartog (2008) expanded ethical leadership dimensions to seven, including fairness, power sharing, role clarification, people-oriented behavior, integrity, ethical guidance, and concern for sustainability. However, Yukl (2011) argues that only honesty, integrity, fairness, and altruism are relevant dimensions, dismissing others as irrelevant. Yukl et al. (2013) further consolidate ethical leadership dimensions into honesty, integrity, fairness, altruism, consistency with espoused values, communication of ethical values, and providing ethical guidance.

Considering the critique and evaluation of ethical leadership dimensions, the study adopts Yukl et al.'s (2013) uni-dimensional ethical leadership questionnaire, comprising eight relevant items, to ensure clarity and consistency in measurement.

The Influence of Ethical Leadership on the Performance

Numerous studies have investigated the impact of ethical leadership on organizational outcomes. Bhatti et al. (2021) demonstrated that ethical leadership influences project success through trust and knowledge sharing. Ashfaq et al. (2021) and Chinwe et al. (2017) revealed that ethical leadership affects employee work engagement via self-efficacy and organizational commitment. Malik et al. (2016) and Nauman and Qamar (2018) highlighted the positive effect of ethical leadership on employee performance and productivity. Similar findings were reported by Qing et al. (2019) and Yozgat and Mesikiran (2016), who identified a correlation between ethical leadership, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment.

Kim and Brymer (2011) and Guo (2022) underscored ethical leadership's impact on manager job satisfaction, commitment, and firm performance. Rantika and Yustina (2017) indicated a relationship between ethical leadership and employee well-being mediated by psychological empowerment.

Conversely, Schyns and Schilling (2013) identified a link between destructive leadership and counterproductive behavior, echoed by Bagyo (2018), Shen & Lei (2022), and Sypniewska (2020). Kilic and Gunsel (2019) further revealed that poor leadership diminishes workplace performance and productivity, impacting employees' behavior, psychology, and job performance.

Overview of Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) originates from political philosophy, with citizenship encompassing obedience, loyalty, and participation (Graham, 1991). Obedience involves adhering to structures and

processes, loyalty extends to considering others' interests and defending the organization, while participation entails engagement in governance (Graham, 1991).

In the organizational context, OCB reflects obedience to structures and policies, loyalty to the organization, and participation in its governance (Inkeles, 1969). This aligns with earlier research defining OCB as behaviors exceeding role requirements (Bateman & Organ, 1983; Smith, Organ, & Near, 1983), akin to citizenship responsibilities.

Katz (1964) identified three key behaviors crucial for organizational functioning: entering and remaining in the system, fulfilling role requirements, and engaging in spontaneous activities beyond prescribed duties. Cooperation and prosocial gestures contribute to internal equilibrium (Roethlisberger & Dickson, 1964).

Efforts to delineate OCB dimensions have evolved, emphasizing loyalty and participation (Graham, 1991; Organ & Ryan, 1995). Dimensions include conscientiousness, sportsmanship, civic virtue, courtesy, and altruism (Organ, 1988; Wang et al., 2013). Podsakoff et al. (2000) identified seven dimensions, encompassing helping behaviors, sportsmanship, organizational loyalty, compliance, individual initiative, civic virtue, and self-development.

Various researchers' dimensions of OCB coalesce into altruistic behavior, encompassing actions benefiting others and the organization (Fox & Spector, 2002).

Conceptual Frameworks

Figure 1: the conceptual framework explains the relationship between ethical leadership and organizational citizenship behavior. The framework indicates that ethical leadership can affect organizational citizenship behavior

Statement of the Problems

The study aims to determine the effects of ethical leadership on the organizational citizenship behavior of the employees. It specifically seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the ethical leadership of administrators of the Divine Word College of Laoag?
2. What is the organizational citizenship behavior of the employees in terms of:
 - a. OCBP (acts that are directed toward a person)
 - b. OCBO: Acts that direct toward an organization).
3. Is there a relationship between ethical leadership and organizational citizenship behavior?

Assumption of the Study

The study assumes that ethical leadership plays an important role in shaping the behavior of the followers. The leading by-example principle suggests that a leader's behavior can influence employees to follow their leader

The results of the studies indicate that ethical leadership affects employees' helping behavior (Yousaf, et.al., 2020) and employees' ethical behavior (Al Halbasi, et.al., 2021). The current study hypothesizes that the ethical behavior of administrators affects the organizational citizenship behavior of the employees.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study limits its investigation to ethical leadership as a single-dimensional construct and organizational citizenship behavior along with OCBP and OCBO and the population is only the employees of the Divine Word College of Laoag.

Research Methodology

The research employed a quantitative approach, utilizing a descriptive and correlational design to evaluate ethical leadership among administrators and its impact on organizational citizenship behavior. Descriptive research offers a comprehensive overview of collected data through questionnaires and statistical analysis, shedding light on the characteristics of individuals, situations, phenomena, or relational variables. This method unveils insights into "what is" within the data (Ariola, 2006, as cited by Abun, 2019). In this study, descriptive assessment and correlational analysis were utilized to ascertain leadership competency levels and their influence on work engagement.

Locale of the Study

The locale of the study was Divine Word Colleges of Laoag, Laoag City, Ilocos Norte

Population

The study was conducted with the participation of all employees and faculty members of Divine Word College of Laoag, Ilocos Norte, making up the population of the study. The total number of respondents was 176, using the method of complete enumeration sampling.

Data Gathering Procedures

The researcher obtained permission from the Presidents of the Colleges to distribute the questionnaires to the students. They personally met with both the Presidents and the students to solicit their participation. The retrieval of the questionnaires was coordinated between the Presidents' representatives and the researcher, facilitated by college staff and faculty members.

Data Gathering Instruments

The current study used research questionnaires to gather the data. The questionnaires are adopted from Yukl, et.al. (2013) on ethical leadership and Fox, et al. (2012) on organizational citizenship behavior.

Ethical Review

The paper underwent submission to the ethical review committee, which waived the review process due to the study's lack of involvement with vulnerable subjects or sensitive data.

Statistical Treatment of Data

As the study employed a descriptive assessment and correlational research design, descriptive and inferential statistics were utilized. Descriptive statistics, particularly the weighted mean, were used to determine the level of ethical leadership and organizational citizenship behavior. The correlation between ethical leadership and organizational citizenship behavior was measured using Pearson's r.

The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation will be used:

<i>Statistical Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
4.21-5.00	Strongly Agree/Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree/High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat Agree/Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree/Low
1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree/Very Low

Data Presentation and Analysis

The data that were gathered through research questionnaires are presented below. The presentation follows the statement of the problems.

Problem 1: What is the ethical leadership of administrators of the Divine Word College of Laoag?

Table 1. Ethical leadership of administrators of Divine Word College of Laoag (n=160)

ETHICAL LEADERSHIP OF ADMINISTRATORS		WEIGHTED MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE INTERPRETATION
1.	Shows a strong concern for ethical and moral values	3.75	A/H
2.	Communicates clear ethical standards for members	3.72	A/H
3.	Sets an example of ethical behavior in his/her decisions and actions	3.62	A/H
4.	Is honest and can be trusted to tell the truth	3.73	A/H
5.	Insists on doing what is fair and ethical even when it is not easy	3.68	A/H
6.	Talks about the importance of honesty and integrity	3.70	A/H
7.	Can be trusted to carry out promises and commitments	3.74	A/H
8.	Holds members accountable for using ethical practices in their work	3.71	A/H
Composite Mean		3.70	A/H

Source: Yukl, et al. (2013)

Legend:

Range of Mean Values	Descriptive Interpretation
4.21 - 5.00	Strongly agree/Very high
3.41 - 4.20	Agree/High
2.61 - 3.40	Somewhat agree/Moderate
1.81 - 2.60	Disagree/Low
1.00 - 1.80	Strongly disagree/Very low

Based on the table data, it's evident that administrators' ethical leadership received an overall composite mean rating of 3.70, indicating an "agree/high" interpretation. This suggests that while not exceptionally high, administrators' ethical leadership is still notably strong. Individual indicators also consistently achieved similar mean ratings, all interpreted as "agree/high." These findings imply that employees perceive administrators as having a robust commitment to moral values, setting ethical standards, exemplifying ethical behavior, and maintaining trustworthiness (Yukl et al., 2013). Guo (2022) and Malik et al. (2016) emphasize that such ethical leadership fosters positive employee conduct, leading to improved job satisfaction, performance, and organizational outcomes.

Problem 2: What is the organizational citizenship behavior of the employees in terms of:
 a. OCBP
 b. OCBO

Table 2. Organizational citizenship behavior of the employees in terms of OCBP (n=160)

ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR		WEIGHTED MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE INTERPRETATION
A.	Acts that Direct toward the person (OCBP)		
1.	Lent a compassionate ear when someone has a work problem	3.68	A/H
2.	Lent a compassionate ear when someone has a personal problem	3.66	A/H
3.	Change vacation schedules, workdays, or shifts to accommodate co-workers' needs	3.66	A/H
4.	Help a less capable co-worker lift a heavy box or other objects	3.70	A/H
5.	Went out of the way to encourage co-workers or express appreciation	3.66	A/H
6.	Defended co-worker who was being 'put down' or spoken ill by other co-workers or supervisors	3.71	A/H
7.	Help co-workers with personal matters such as sharing food or drinks	3.68	A/H
8.	Lent money or personal property to a co-worker	3.64	A/H
Composite Mean		3.66	A/H

The table data reveals that employees' organizational citizenship behavior regarding concern for others (OCBP) received an overall composite mean rating of 3.66, indicating an interpretation of "agree/high." This suggests a notable level of organizational citizenship behavior in terms of concern for others, falling between moderate and high. Individual indicators also consistently achieved high mean ratings. Employees demonstrate a willingness to listen to coworkers' work-related and personal issues, make sacrifices for their colleagues, and provide motivation and encouragement. Research by Lilius et al. (2003) links workplace compassion to positive emotions, reduced job-related stress, increased organizational commitment, and enhanced psychological well-being, supported by findings from Kirby, Tellegen, and Steindl (2017) regarding decreased anxiety and psychological distress.

Table 3: Organizational Citizenship Behavior in terms of OCBO

	ORGANIZATIONAL BEHAVIOR	CITIZENSHIP	WEIGHTED MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE INTERPRETATION
B.	Acts that Direct toward the organization (OCBO)			
1.	Help new employees get oriented to the job		3.75	A/H
2.	Offered suggestions to improve how work is done		3.68	A/H
3.	Volunteered for extra work assignments		3.61	A/H
4.	Said good things about your employer in front of others		3.68	A/H
5.	Said good things about your school in the community outside the school		3.83	A/H
6.	Give up meals and other breaks to complete the work		3.69	A/H
7.	Offered suggestions for improving the work environment		3.65	A/H
8.	came in early or stayed late without pay to complete a project or task		3.72	A/H
9.	Volunteer to share new job knowledge or skills with other employees		3.65	A/H
	Composite Mean		3.67	A/H
	OVERALL MEAN (OCBP & OCBO)		3.68	

Source: Spector and Fox (2002)

Legend:

<i>Range of Mean Values</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
4.21 - 5.00	Strongly agree/Very High
3.41 - 4.20	Agree/high
2.61 - 3.40	Somewhat agree/moderate
1.81 - 2.60	Disagree/Low
1.00 - 1.80	Strongly disagree/Very low

The table data indicates that employees' organizational behavior regarding concern for the organization (OCBO) received an overall composite mean rating of 3.68, interpreted as "agree/high." This suggests a high level of organizational citizenship behavior in terms of concern for the organization. Individual indicators also consistently achieved high mean ratings. Employees engage in activities such as assisting new hires, suggesting improvements, volunteering for extra tasks, promoting the institution and employers, foregoing breaks to complete tasks, and sharing knowledge with colleagues (Spector & Fox, 2002). Nakase (2023) and Yaakobi and Weisberg (2020) assert that such organizational citizenship behavior fosters positive work environments, enhances job satisfaction, engagement, well-being, and organizational performance.

Problem 3: Is there a relationship between ethical leadership and the organizational citizenship behavior of the employees?

Table 4: Relationship between Ethical leadership and Organizational citizenship behavior

ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR OF EMPLOYEES	ETHICAL LEADERSHIP OF ADMINISTRATORS	
Acts that Direct Toward the Person (OCBP)	r	.174*
	(Sig. 2 - tailed)	.028
Acts that Direct Toward the organization (OCBO)	r	.153
	(Sig. 2-tailed)	.053

* Significant at .05 level of significance (2-tailed)

** Significant at .01 level of significance (2-tailed)

Ethical Leadership of Administrators and OCBP (Acts that are Directed Toward a Person)

The correlation coefficient of .174 between administrators' ethical leadership and employees' organizational citizenship behavior directed toward individuals (OCBP) is positive and significant at the .05 level. This suggests a meaningful relationship between the two variables. As administrators' ethical leadership increases, employees' OCBP also tends to increase. Thus, employees under administrators with higher ethical leadership levels demonstrate more ethical behaviors toward individuals compared to those under administrators with lower ethical leadership levels.

Ethical Leadership of Administrators and OCBO (Acts that Directed Toward the Organization)

The correlation coefficient of .153 between administrators' ethical leadership and employees' organizational citizenship behavior directed toward the organization (OCBO) is not significant at the .05 level. This suggests that administrators' ethical leadership does not influence employees' OCBO. Therefore, regardless of administrators' ethical leadership levels, employees' OCBO remains unchanged.

Results and Discussions

The findings indicate that while ethical leadership and organizational citizenship behavior (OCBP & OCBO) are high, they are not exceedingly so. However, ethical leadership does not significantly impact overall organizational citizenship behavior among employees. Yet, examining OCBP separately reveals that administrators' ethical leadership influences employees' concern for coworkers. Higher ethical standards among administrators correlate with increased compassion among employees for each other. However, this does not extend to organizational concerns. Thus, ethical leadership appears crucial for fostering compassion among employees toward one another, as observed in the context of the Divine Word College of Laoag. This finding contradicts the study of Huang et al. (2021).

Conclusion

The study finds that both ethical leadership and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) among employees are high. However, the Pearson correlation shows that while ethical leadership correlates with OCB directed toward individuals (OCBP), it is not correlated with OCB directed toward the organization (OCBO). This

suggests a need for further research to explore additional aspects of leadership that may influence employees' organizational citizenship.

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